

DIASTOLIC DYSFUNCTION OF THE RIGHT VENTRICLE IN PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC PULMONARY HEART DISEASE IN THE CONTEXT OF COMPREHENSIVE TREATMENT (EMPHASIS ON THE VASOREGULATORY FUNCTION OF THE ENDOTHELIUM)

Normatova K.Sh.
Karimov M.Sh.
Tukhtaeva N.Kh.
Azimova M.M.

Tashkent Medical Academy, Tashkent, Uzbekistan.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14969990>

Relevance. In recent years, Uzbekistan has observed an increase in the prevalence and mortality of lung diseases complicated by pulmonary arterial hypertension (PAH) and chronic pulmonary heart disease (CPHD). For the early diagnosis, adequate prevention, and treatment of CPHD, it is essential to clarify the factors that lead to its development and exacerbate its course¹.

Objective of the Study. To examine the condition of diastolic function of the right ventricle (RV), pulmonary hemodynamics, and the vasoregulatory function of the endothelium of peripheral vessels in patients with CPHD during comprehensive treatment.

Materials and Methods. A total of 53 patients with COPD (average age: 49.7 ± 2.8 years, disease duration: 10.7 ± 2.9 years) whose condition was complicated by PAH with a mean pulmonary arterial pressure (mPAP) exceeding 25 mmHg were examined. Additionally, 40 COPD patients (average age: 56.9 ± 2.6 years, disease duration: 16.8 ± 3.7 years) with RV hypertrophy and 20 healthy individuals were included.

The patients were randomized into three subgroups based on their treatment methods:

- **Subgroup A:** 14 COPD patients with RV hypertrophy (1a) and 17 COPD patients with PAH (2a) receiving basic therapy (BT).

- **Subgroup B:** 12 COPD patients with RV hypertrophy (1b) and 17 COPD patients with PAH (2b) receiving BT with amlodipine (5–10 mg/day) and ozone therapy (OT).

- **Subgroup C:** 14 COPD patients with RV hypertrophy (1c) and 19 COPD patients with PAH (2c) receiving BT combined with OT.

Basic therapy included:

β -agonists + anticholinergic inhalers, anti-leukotrienes, methylxanthines, β -agonists, glucocorticosteroids, along with ImmunoHelp capsules (1 capsule,

three times daily), chest massage, and breathing exercises. The effectiveness of treatment regimens was evaluated dynamically on the 10th day of therapy.

Psycho-emotional status was assessed through psychological testing for reactive anxiety (RA) and personal anxiety (PA).

Endothelium-dependent vasodilation (EDVD) was evaluated via Doppler imaging of the brachial artery (BA), measuring the maximal systolic blood flow velocity (MSV, m/s) and vascular resistance index (VRI, units) in response to a compression test (CT).

Doppler echocardiography assessed diastolic function indicators, mean pulmonary arterial pressure levels, and the stable metabolites of nitric oxide (SMNO) in plasma.

Results. The study revealed that COPD patients with CPHD exhibit an imbalance in SMNO levels in plasma and reduced capacity for active EDVD in BA. Analysis of reactive hyperemia tests demonstrated a significant reduction in MSV among CPHD patients, correlating with disease severity. Compared to healthy individuals, MSV in CPHD patients decreased by 32.9% and 19.2%, respectively, while VRI increased by 38.6% and 28.0%. Along with impaired EDVD, diastolic dysfunction of the RV was observed. Notably, RV dysfunction positively correlated with SMNO levels ($r=0.32$, $p<0.05$).

Conclusions.

1. The most pronounced reduction in SMNO levels, EDVD, and affective symptoms was observed in COPD patients with RV hypertrophy compared to those with PAH. RV dysfunction positively correlated with SMNO levels ($r=0.32$, $p<0.05$).

2. OT and amlodipine in combination with BT significantly normalized SMNO levels, improving EDVD and RV diastolic function, reducing mPAP, and alleviating affective symptoms in COPD patients with CPHD complications.

